

FINANCIAL LIABILITIES: ESSENCE AND ACCOUNTING

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Abstract: All the activities of the state are connected with finance. Their importance has especially increased in connection with the acquisition of state sovereignty of the Republic of Uzbekistan and when the society focused on the formation of a market economy, free movement of goods, services and financial resources, support for competition and freedom of economic activity. Constitutional recognition and State protection of all forms of property have become more important than ever.

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Introduction.

In the course of its activities, the company interacts with other organizations, individuals. individuals, as well as with the authorities. As a result of such interaction, the organization has various kinds of obligations – financial, property, and others.

Financial obligations for businesses are like credit cards for individuals. They are convenient because the company can use "other people's money" to finance its business activities for a certain period of time, which lasts until the maturity date specified in the contract. But excessive monetary obligations can damage the business and put the company on the verge of bankruptcy.

Occurrence and accounting of financial liabilities

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What are the financial obligations of an organization?

The concept of "financial liabilities" is defined in IAS 32 "Financial Instruments: Presentation". There is no clear definition in the Russian legislation. Under IFRS, an entity's financial liability is one of the following elements:

a contractual obligation to transfer money or other financial assets to another entity;

exchange of financial assets on unfavorable terms for the company;

a contract that is subject to settlement at the expense of the company's own capital

In simple terms, the financial obligations of a company are all payments that it must make in accordance with the concluded agreements. These include accounts payable to suppliers and contractors, debts under loan and credit agreements, including outstanding guarantees, and so on.

Financial obligations are not only for commercial enterprises, but also for individuals. individuals, banks, and the state. To the obligations of the individual. individuals include debts on loans, debts for housing and communal services, unpaid taxes, fines, etc. The rest of the positions will be considered below.

Financial liabilities of the Bank

The obligations of a bank are different from the debts of a commercial organization. If the latter in most cases carry out activities at the expense of their own finances, then the basis of banking operations is the funds raised.

The bank's financial liabilities are divided into 2 groups:
deposit and non-
deposit liabilities

The first item includes funds deposited by individuals, individuals and organizations to bank accounts and used in accordance with the concluded agreement. Non-deposit liabilities include funds raised in the form of loans taken by the bank or received from the sale of debt securities on the market.

In both cases, the bank pays for the use of the attracted money. In the case of deposit financial obligations, this is the interest to depositors for keeping money in the account, and in the case of non – deposit obligations, this is the loan interest and coupon income.

The bank's profitability condition: interest on financial liabilities should be less than the rates on assets. For the bank, the assets are loans issued, investment investments, etc. Therefore, it is not surprising that with a deposit rate of 5% per annum in rubles, the rate on loans (issued loans) in the same bank may well be 10-15% per year and even higher.

In an attempt to increase profits, many of the largest banks enter into swap contracts with other financial institutions. For example, the bank expects that in the foreseeable future, the US index will bring significantly below the historical average return of 10% per year. He finds an investment company that agrees to pay a fixed income of 5% per annum in foreign currency, receiving a positive index result from

the bank. Thus, the expectations of the participants of the transaction are opposite, but the company is insured against heavy losses with a premium of 5%.

To make it easier for a company to account for and track its financial liabilities, they are divided into long-term and short-term, as well as current and overdue.

1. Short-term financial obligations must be fulfilled within one production cycle or within 12 months after the conclusion of the contract. All other debts of the company are recognized as long-term.

2. Current financial obligations are still waiting to be fulfilled. They are normal for every enterprise.

3. Overdue debts are considered to be those that have already passed their due date. Such debts entail additional costs for the company in the form of penalties.

Accounting for financial liabilities

In accounting, there are a number of differences regarding financial liabilities under NSB and IFRS, although in both cases they are reflected in the liabilities section. Thus, according to the Russian standard, accounting for financial liabilities is carried out at the original cost stipulated by the terms of the concluded contract, and is not subject to change until the date of full or partial fulfillment of the obligation.

In accordance with IFRS, cash is taken at fair value and subsequently carried at either fair value or amortised cost. Fair value is considered to be the value that could be obtained by transferring liabilities under current market conditions. Amortized is the initial price of the debt less the amount actually repaid.

For example, the company took a loan of 100 thousand. At registration the insurance of 5 thousand and the bank commission of 2 thousand was paid. The fair

value of the loan will be calculated as the cost of the contract minus the costs incurred, that is, 93 thousand.

Any organization has financial obligations in the course of its activities, which implies the need to take them into account. On the one hand, they serve as one of the sources of capital for operating activities, and on the other hand, they are future expenses of the enterprise when their repayment date comes. If the company's financial liabilities significantly exceed its own capital, this indicates its dependence on other counterparties and its own financial instability.

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